

Measles Elimination Challenges in Sub-Saharan Africa: The Critical Role of Vaccine Acceptance

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ABSTRACT

Measles is a highly infectious disease. Despite the existence of effective vaccines, the disease remains a significant issue in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), with a massive burden on children. Countries in this region have low measles vaccination coverage. This study, therefore, sought to assess measles vaccine acceptance in this region and its determinants to inform disease control.

A cross-sectional survey was conducted in countries in the SSA from January to December 2025. Data on participants' willingness to vaccinate their children were collected using online and in-person questionnaires in the selected countries. The chi-square test identified elements associated with vaccine acceptance. Multiple logistic regression depicted determinants of vaccine acceptance. SPSS enabled analysis, and a p-value < 0.05 was considered significant. Microsoft Excel 365 was used to elaborate on charts and tables.

Data was collected from 4,109 people in 17 countries. Measles vaccine acceptance rate varied from 75 to 99%. Participants from low- to middle-income backgrounds, health-related fields, and with higher education levels, were more willing to vaccinate their children. Determinants to accept vaccine included knowledge of measles (OR = 2.2, 95% CI: 1.3-3.7, p < 0.01), education level (OR = 0.7, 95% CI: 0.4-0.8, p < 0.01), and female gender (OR = 0.4, 95% CI: 0.2-0.7, p < 0.01).

Hesitancy was linked to vaccine safety issues, health system distrust, and religious beliefs. Measles remains a critical issue in SSA. Leveraging vaccine acceptance, addressing vaccine hesitancy, and strengthening countries' vaccine service delivery will facilitate vaccine uptake and measles elimination.

1. Introduction

Measles is a highly infectious viral disease causing serious health complications, particularly in children under five years.¹ This disease has a considerable burden on the population. In 2024, measles cost the lives of about 95,000 people worldwide, most of whom were children under five and unvaccinated.² Measles-containing vaccines play a crucial role in disease control. Measles vaccination averted approximately 59 million deaths between 2000 and 2024.³

The World Health Organization (WHO) African Region has made some progress in measles control in recent years. In 2024, compared to 2019, the region observed a 40% reduction in measles cases and a 50% decline in deaths, partly due to increasing immunization coverage.⁴ Despite this tremendous progress, resource-constrained settings, like those in the African region, continue to face a challenging disease burden. Over 30 million children worldwide remained vulnerable to the disease in 2024, and a considerable number are in challenging settings in regions like Africa.⁵

In addition, sub-Saharan African (SSA) nations continue to bear a heavy disease burden. This region suffers from suboptimal vaccination coverage.⁶ The situation puts the

population at a high burden of vaccine-preventable diseases.⁷ Countries in the SSA region are among the top 10 most affected by measles.⁸ This study, therefore, sought to investigate the role of measles vaccine acceptance, its drivers, and vaccine hesitancy factors in SSA that contribute to suboptimal vaccination coverage and the failure to eliminate measles.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study design

This cross-sectional survey was conducted in 17 countries in SSA. The study targeted participants aged 18 to 67 across the included countries from January to December 2025. An online questionnaire in KoboToolbox was used to collect data from all participants who consented and completed the form.

2.2 Study setting

The SSA region includes countries south of the Sahara Desert. This zone comprises 50 countries.⁹ The region has a population of about 1.3 billion inhabitants.¹⁰ The SSA region includes countries with the world's highest measles burden, such as Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of Congo.¹¹ These nations also contribute to the highest rates of unvaccinated children.¹²

¹ CDC, 'About Measles', Measles (Rubeola), 9 April 2025, 1, <https://www.cdc.gov/measles/about/index.html>.

² WHO, 'Measles', 28 November 2025, 1, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/measles>.

³ WHO, 'Measles', 1–2.

⁴ WHO, 'Measles Deaths down 88% since 2000, but Cases Surge', 28 November 2025, 1, <https://www.who.int/news/item/28-11-2025-measles-deaths-down-88--since-2000--but-cases-surge>.

⁵ WHO, 'Measles Deaths down 88% since 2000, but Cases Surge', 1.

⁶ David Jean Simon et al., 'Regional, Subregional and Country-Level Full Vaccination Coverage in Children Aged 12–23 Months for 34 Countries in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Global Analysis Using Demographic and Health Survey Data', *BMJ Global Health* 10, no. 3 (2025): 4–6, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2024-018333>.

⁷ Jean Paul Sinumvayo et al., 'Vaccination and Vaccine-Preventable Diseases in Africa', *Scientific African* 24 (June 2024): 2–4, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2024.e02199>.

⁸ CDC, 'Global Measles Outbreaks', Global Measles Vaccination, 13 January 2026, 1, <https://www.cdc.gov/global-measles-vaccination/data-research/global-measles-outbreaks/index.html>.

⁹ The World Academy of Sciences (TWAS), 'Sub-Saharan African Countries', accessed 29 January 2026, <https://twas.org/sub-saharan-african-countries>.

¹⁰ Amy McKenna, 'Sub-Saharan Africa', 27 January 2026, 1, <https://www.britannica.com/place/sub-Saharan-Africa>.

¹¹ CDC, 'Global Measles Outbreaks', Global Measles Vaccination, 12 November 2025, 1, <https://www.cdc.gov/global-measles-vaccination/data-research/global-measles-outbreaks/index.html>.

¹² Karen McClorey Hackett, 'Eight Countries Contain Most Zero-Dose Children', 25 June 2025, 1, <https://www.vax-before-travel.com/2025/06/25/eight-countries-contain-most-zero-dose-children>.

The study countries included Algeria, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Democratic Republic of Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Republic of Congo, Republic of Guinea, Togo, and Zambia.

2.3 Study questionnaire

Data was collected using an online questionnaire. The questionnaire was adapted from a vaccine acceptance study conducted in Cameroon.¹³ The questionnaire was further adjusted following a measles vaccine acceptance study in Cameroon. The questionnaire was pretested with 50 participants in Cameroon, Chad, Nigeria, and Equatorial Guinea and revised to enhance clarity. The tool had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.74.

The questionnaire was available in English, French, and Spanish to facilitate understanding among participants in the study countries. Additionally, the questions were semi-open-ended, enabling participants to select their answers and add comments when necessary. Also, the responses were anonymous.

The questionnaire collected participants' information, including their country of residence, region/province, community type (urban/rural), gender, job type, and income level. Income level was classified according to the four-level classification highlighted by Gapminder.¹⁴ The questionnaire also captured data on measles vaccine knowledge, family history of measles, and death. The form also asked whether the participant would accept vaccination of their child against measles and the reasons for accepting or refusing the vaccine.

Respondents had to answer all questions to be able to submit the form online.

2.4 Study sample Size

The Raosoft sample size calculator was used to estimate the minimum sample size, factoring in an estimated population of nearly 1.3 billion in the SSA region, a 5% error margin, and a 95% confidence interval. The calculator estimated that at least 385 participants would need to be recruited in the SSA region.¹⁵ This recruitment target ensured that participants were representative for adequate statistical analysis in the study site.

2.5 Participants recruitment

The participants were recruited through each country's Ministry of Health's existing dialogue structure. The study was presented to the Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI) and other senior-level country managers. These actors then shared the study information with sub-national level managers. These actors informed the populations in their health areas of the research benefits, the participant time burden, and the need for internet access for online submission of the form, using existing dialogue structures.

A simple random sampling permitted the recruitment of participants in the various dialogue structure levels. The dialogue structure actors mobilized the community through their local channels, and those interested were selected manually using a random-order table and then provided with the online questionnaire. Getting respondents was challenging in some countries through the dialogue structure. So, The Njoh Foundation (TNF) recruited local volunteers who supported population mobilization and participant recruitment. They

¹³ Andreas Ateke Njoh et al., 'Malaria Vaccine Acceptance and Associated Factors in Cameroon: A Nationwide Cross-Sectional Survey', *Vaccine* 60 (July 2025): 2, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2025.127323>.

¹⁴ Gapminder, *Four Regions*, n.d., 5, accessed 12 July 2023, <https://www.gapminder.org/fw/four-regions/>.

¹⁵ Raosoft, 'Sample Size Calculator by Raosoft, Inc.', Raosoft, Inc, 2004, 1, <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>.

also provided some participants with their smartphones to access the form and to submit the completed questionnaire online. WhatsApp and other social media platforms were used to share the questionnaire with potential participants. Included respondents were those aged 18 and older who consented to participate.

2.6 Data analysis

Analysis was done through IBM SPSS. Participants' demographic and other characteristics were presented with descriptive statistics. The Chi-square test identified the relationship between the variables and acceptance of the measles vaccine. All analyses were binary based on whether the respondents would accept the measles vaccine for their infants. Excel was used to group participants' similar comments and explanations into proportions for each question.

Vaccine acceptance was expressed as the proportion of respondents willing to vaccinate their children against measles, by country. The reasons for accepting and denying the vaccine were graded using respondents' comments to the semi-open-ended question, "Why will you accept to vaccinate your child against measles?" and "Why will you not accept to vaccinate your child against measles?" Multiple logistic regression was used to depict factors associated with vaccine acceptance. A p -value < 0.05 was used for all statistical tests. Microsoft Excel 365 facilitated the creation of charts and tables.

This research obtained ethical clearance from the Cameroon National Ethics Committee for Research on Human Health, N° 2024/07/1699/CE/CNERSH/SP.

3. Results

The research captured data from 4,109 respondents representing 17 SSA countries. These nations included Nigeria

and countries with which they have free circulation, such as Cameroon and other nations of the Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS) and the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). Nations within each region experience free movement of people and trade across their borders. In addition, bilateral collaboration facilitates the free movement of people and trade across countries in different regions, such as between Cameroon and Nigeria.

Table 1: Measles Vaccine Acceptance per country

Countries	Vaccine acceptance		
	Respondents per country	Accept to vaccinate infants	Acceptance proportion
Cameroon	2,169	2,144	99%
Nigeria	580	550	95%
Rep. of Congo	416	397	95%
Chad	295	289	98%
Gabon	138	104	75%
Eq. Guinea	123	108	88%
Other countries	388	286	96%
Total	4,109	3,961	96%

Rep: Republic, Eq: Equatorial

Table 1 presents the measles vaccination acceptance rate by country. Other countries in the table report vaccine acceptance rates of n countries with few (388) respondents.

The acceptance rate varies by country, with a global average of 96% (Table 1). In the other countries, the acceptance rate was 286 participants, willing to vaccinate their children against measles, from Algeria, Burkina Faso, Togo, Mali, Ghana, the Republic of Guinea, and Zambia. The vaccine acceptance rates were lower for the Central African Republic (93%), the Democratic Republic of Congo (97%), the Ivory Coast (83%), and Niger (89%). The least acceptance rate was in Gabon (75%).

This figure presents the reasons participants were willing to have their children receive the measles vaccine. Each color depicts a reason.

Figure 1: Reasons for Measles Vaccine Acceptance

Several factors motivated parents to have their children vaccinated (Figure 1). Some key factors included the desire to protect the children and keep them healthy. Additionally, many parents hope to prevent the spread of measles and protect others. In Table 2, several variables associated with parents' willingness to vaccinate their children were statistically significant. The youngest age groups (18-27 and 28-37 years) were less likely to accept the vaccine for their children. People with higher levels of education reported a greater desire to vaccinate their children. There was no difference in vaccine acceptance between people in urban and rural settings.

Table 2: Measles Vaccine Acceptance Elements

N=4109	Modalities		Vaccine acceptance (%)	P-value
	Variable	n		
Parents' age (years)	18-27	542	521 (96)	0.05
	28-37	1,313	1,251 (95)	
	38-47	1,242	1,207 (97)	
	48-58	841	814 (97)	
	58 and above	171	168 (98)	
Gender	Female	1,693	1,659 (98)	<0.01
	Male	2,416	2,302 (95)	
Income level	Low income	1,456	1,426 (98)	<0.01
	Middle income	1,368	1,280 (94)	
	High income	1,068	1,053 (99)	
	Higher income	217	202 (93)	
Occupation	Business	244	232 (95)	<0.01
	Engineer/Technician	247	237 (96)	
	Healthcare professional	2,207	2,186 (99)	
	Politician/Administrator	81	70 (86)	
	Teaching	236	190 (81)	
	Unemployed	477	451 (95)	
	Others	617	595 (96)	
	Level of education	No formal education	37	
Primary	120	112 (93)		
Secondary and high school	861	795 (92)		
University	2,001	1,957 (98)		
Vocational training	1,090	1,063 (98)		
Family measles history	No	2172	2,119 (98)	<0.01
	Yes	1,307	1,277 (98)	
	I don't know	536	481 (89)	
Family history of	No	3,388	3,301 (97)	

measles death				
	Yes	298	282(95)	<0.01
	I don't know	332	300(90)	
	Rural	1,818	1,752(96)	0.9
Residence	Urban	2291	2,209(96)	

Table 2 presents the elements associated with measles vaccine acceptance, as assessed using the chi-square test.

Several factors predicted measles vaccine acceptance in the 17 countries (Figure 2). These determinants included knowledge of measles (OR = 22, 95% CI: 13-37, $p < 0.01$), education level (OR = 0.6, 95% CI: 0.4-0.8, $p < 0.01$), and female gender (OR = 0.4, 95% CI: 0.2-0.7, $p < 0.01$). Additionally, individuals with professional occupations had higher odds of accepting the vaccine (Supplementary Table 1). Also, people with a family history of measles death had a greater odds of agreeing to vaccinate their children. Still, a family history of measles did not have a statistically significant impact on whether parents would accept the vaccine for their children.

Figure 2 depicts the determinants of parents' acceptance of the measles vaccine for children using a multilogistic regression model.

Figure 2: Key Predictors of Measles Vaccine Acceptance for Children using multilogistic regression

Despite an overall measles vaccination acceptance rate of 96% across the region, hesitancy to vaccinate infants persists. This 4% average unwillingness to vaccinate was due to various factors (Figure 3). The key elements associated with parents' measles vaccine hesitancy for their children include concerns about vaccine safety, a lack of trust in the healthcare system, and the use of traditional remedies to address the disease (Figure 3). Challenges in reaching the health facility, confusing social media messages, and vaccine costs also pose problems.

Figure 3 highlights the elements reported by participants, which motivate the unwillingness to accept vaccination in the 17 countries.

Figure 3: Key Elements Driving Measles Vaccine Hesitancy Among

4. Discussion

Measles remains a significant global health challenge, affecting every nation and imposing a considerable burden in Africa.¹⁶ The disease hits sub-Saharan African countries due to suboptimal vaccination coverage. This study, therefore, sought to investigate the role of measles vaccine acceptance, its drivers, and vaccine hesitancy factors in the study area that contribute to suboptimal vaccination coverage and the failure to eliminate measles.

Assessing 4,109 respondents across 17 SSA countries, the average vaccine acceptance rate was 96%. Participants aged 28 to 47, from low- to middle-income backgrounds, working in health-related fields, and with higher education levels were more likely to be willing to vaccinate their children. Key determinants of vaccine acceptance included parents'

knowledge of the disease, profession, education level, and gender. On the other hand, vaccine hesitancy was driven by concerns about vaccine safety, a lack of trust in the health system, and religious beliefs.

People's willingness to vaccinate enables children to receive vaccines and be protected.¹⁷ Measles outbreaks are strongly linked to declining vaccine acceptance and resulting immunization rates below the critical threshold for herd immunity.¹⁸ The COVID-19 pandemic and the spread of misinformation exacerbated the decline in measles vaccine acceptance in the SSA countries. Although childhood immunization services have been restored following the COVID-19 pandemic, coverage has not returned to pre-pandemic levels, leading to the persistence of measles.¹⁹

The healthcare system should capitalize on the high vaccine acceptance rate reported in this study to facilitate prompt vaccine uptake among the responding populations. Exploring these high acceptance rates across countries and strengthening vaccine service delivery in routine immunization and supplementary immunization activities will increase vaccine coverage and help control the measles epidemic in SSA. This approach will enhance herd immunity and help eliminate measles.

In resource-constrained settings, such as in SSA, socioeconomic status (SES) significantly affects vaccine acceptance, with lower SES often associated with lower acceptance rates due to barriers to healthcare and information,

¹⁶ WHO, 'Measles Deaths down 88% since 2000, but Cases Surge', 1.

¹⁷ Njoh et al., 'Malaria Vaccine Acceptance and Associated Factors in Cameroon', 4–6.

¹⁸ Uraiwan Sirithammaphan et al., 'Barriers to Measles Mumps Rubella Vaccine Acceptance in the Three Southern Border Provinces of Thailand',

Clinical and Experimental Vaccine Research 12, no. 4 (2023): 2, <https://doi.org/10.7774/cevr.2023.12.4.298>.

¹⁹ Jessica Kaufman et al., 'The Case for Assessing the Drivers of Measles Vaccine Uptake', *Vaccines* 12, no. 6 (2024): 1–2, <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines12060692>.

as well as greater mistrust of institutions.²⁰ Elements contributing to this complexity include lower educational attainment, which can correlate with lower health literacy, and financial constraints that can make it challenging to access healthcare services or take time off work for vaccinations. In addition, SES heavily influences measles risk: poorer communities, lacking access to healthcare and education, and facing overcrowding, experience higher outbreaks and deaths due to lower vaccination rates.²¹ Conversely, higher SES can lead to greater access to reliable health information and a greater ability to overcome logistical challenges, fostering higher vaccine acceptance.²²

Although males also had a high vaccine acceptance for children, female gender was a determinant of acceptance in this study population. Women play a crucial role in childcare and access to essential services. This finding aligns with previous studies on the African continent, such as those in Uganda, indicating that, at the household level, mothers are primarily responsible for taking children to vaccination centers.²³ It recognizes that while women are often the primary caregivers responsible for child immunization, their ability to do so is shaped by household decision-making power, access to resources, and exposure to information, all of which are often controlled by the father.

At the individual level, the heavy workload and limited decision-making power of female caregivers hinder their ability to take children to vaccination appointments. At this level, mothers often rely on fathers and depend on men to cover the costs to reach the immunization centers and vaccinate the children.²⁴ This challenge may limit vaccination coverage despite the high acceptance rate in women.

Vaccine hesitancy varied from 25% in Gabon to 1% in Cameroon. It is critical to address hesitancy issues regardless of the percentage. Measles vaccine hesitancy stems from a mix of safety concerns, mistrust in institutions, and powerful social/misinformation influences via social media and family, despite measles's high contagiousness.²⁵ Theories suggest that psychological factors, social drivers, and a lack of confidence drive decisions, requiring multifaceted strategies such as empathetic communication and addressing misinformation to rebuild trust.²⁶ It is critical to simplify information, provide evidence-based advice, make vaccinations accessible, and directly combat misinformation.²⁷ This approach will build confidence in the vaccine and government services, strengthen vaccination coverage, and promote the elimination of measles,

²⁰ Wang *et al.*, "Global Socioeconomic Inequalities in Vaccination Coverage, Supply, and Confidence," *Npj Vaccines* 10, no. 1 (May 2025): 2–5, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41541-025-01143-8>.

²¹ Subekshya Bidari and Wan Yang, 'Global Resurgence of Measles in the Vaccination Era and Influencing Factors', *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 147 (October 2024): 3, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2024.107189>.

²² Darcy Jones McMaughan *et al.*, 'Socioeconomic Status and Access to Healthcare: Interrelated Drivers for Healthy Aging', *Frontiers in Public Health* 8 (June 2020): 3, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00231>.

²³ Adelline Twimukye *et al.*, "Vaccinating a Child Is upon the Woman": Implications for Improving Uptake for the Recently Introduced Second Dose of Measles-Containing Vaccine Based on a Rapid Community Assessment in

Uganda', *Frontiers in Global Women's Health* 6 (April 2025): 1, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgwh.2025.1441242>.

²⁴ Twimukye *et al.*, "Vaccinating a Child Is upon the Woman," 1.

²⁵ Tamara Sedrakyan *et al.*, 'Measles Vaccine Hesitancy among Mothers in Yerevan, Armenia: A Qualitative Study', *Journal of Public Health Research* 14, no. 3 (2025): 8, <https://doi.org/10.1177/22799036251376852>.

²⁶ Kira Anson and Sarah Patel, 'Misinformation and Its Impact on Measles Vaccine Hesitancy in the Pediatric Population: A Scoping Review', *Journal of Pediatric Nursing* 86 (November 2025): 136, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2025.11.008>.

²⁷ Jane Tuckerman *et al.*, 'Effective Approaches to Combat Vaccine Hesitancy', *The Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal* 41, no. 5 (2022): 243–45, <https://doi.org/10.1097/INF.0000000000003499>.

in line with the Measles and Rubella Strategic Framework 2021-2030.²⁸

This research sheds light on vaccine acceptance and hesitancy issues across 17 SSA countries. Its findings guide the contribution of vaccine acceptance to measles control and orient strategies to improve measles vaccination coverage to eliminate the disease. It is the first global health study to depict measles vaccine acceptance in this region, to the best of our knowledge. Despite these merits, the study uses an online questionnaire to capture data from participants. This design could have missed some people and communities with limited internet and device access to answer the questions. To mitigate this potential design challenge, volunteers from TNF supported participants in some communities in accessing and submitting the form online. Additionally, high vaccine acceptance does not necessarily translate into high population vaccination coverage, as various factors affect vaccination rates. So, it is unclear why communities with vaccine acceptance rates as high as 99% like Cameroon, still have measles vaccination coverage below 85%.

It is crucial to investigate why vaccination coverage remains low, despite high measles vaccination acceptance rates in most countries, to inform interventions that address coverage gaps. Additionally, studies on the relationship between women's acceptance of vaccination for their children and their children's vaccination against measles will further inform us about why vaccination coverage remains low in this context. Furthermore, understanding the high vaccine hesitancy in Gabon will guide country-specific interventions to improve vaccine uptake.

5. Conclusion

²⁸ Measles and Rubella Partnership. "Measles & Rubella Strategic Framework 2021-2030," 3-6.

Measles is a highly infectious disease with a considerable impact in SSA. This study presents measles vaccine acceptance in 17 nations and shows highly varying rates across the region. The research identified key determinants of vaccine acceptance, including people's knowledge of the disease, socioeconomic status, and female gender. Leveraging high vaccine acceptance rates across most nations and addressing vaccine hesitancy in the region will improve vaccination coverage and facilitate measles elimination in SSA. There is also a need to assess the factors contributing to the region's low vaccination coverage, despite high vaccine acceptance in most countries.

6. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest that could have influenced this research or the elaboration of this article.

7. Acknowledgment

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8 Funding

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8. Availability of data and materials

The database of this study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

9. List of abbreviations

ECCAS: Economic Community of Central African States,
ECOWAS: Economic Community of West African States, **EPI:**
Expanded Program on Immunization, **SSA:** Sub-Saharan Africa,
SES: socioeconomic status, **TNF:** The Njoh Foundation, **WHO:**
World Health Organization

10. Contributions

AAN conceived the study's idea, design, and elaborated on the first draft. AAN and IM contributed to data collection and analysis. AAN, MGJ, ZH, MAB, FC, revised subsequent drafts. MGJ guided the implementation process. LCK inspired, supervised the research, and guided the preparation of the article. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

11. Ethics declarations and consent to participate

This study received ethical clearance for the research from the National Ethics Committee for Research on Human Health in Cameroon, N° 2024/07/1699/CE/CNERSH/SP. Ministry of Health managers of the involved countries understood the study and shared it with their dialogue structure. Participants consented after understanding the research goal, being informed that there was no risk, and knowing that participating would require them to dedicate their time and use their internet access.

12. Consent for publication

Not applicable.

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Supplementary Table 1: Determinants of parents' acceptance of the measles vaccine for children using a multilogistic regression model.

	Indicator	P-value	OR	95% CI
Education	Level of education	<0.01	0.7	0.5-0.9
Gender	Female	<0.01	0.4	0.2-0.7
	Business	0.7	1.2	0.5-2.7
	Engineer/Technician	0.8	1.1	0.4-2.9
Occupation	Healthcare	0.08	0.5	0.3-1.1
	Politics/Decision Maker/Administrative	0.02	3.1	1.1-8.6
	Teaching	<0.01	3.2	1.5-6.8
	Unemployed/Student	0.28	1.6	0.7-3.8
Income	Low-income	<0.01	0.2	0.1-0.5
	Middle income	0.47	0.8	0.4-1.6
	High income	<0.01	0.2	0.1-0.5
Measles	Measles knowledge	<0.01	22.1	13.2-37.0
	Measles family history	0.59	0.8	0.3-1.8
	Measles death in the family	<0.01	0.3	0.1-0.6
	Measles infection history in the family	0.23	0.7	0.4-1.3
	History of measles in the community	0.29	0.7	0.3-1.4
Age	18-27 years	0.34	0.5	0.1-2.2
	28-37 years	0.79	1.2	0.3-4.4
	38-47 years	0.72	1.3	0.3-4.7
	48-57 years	0.88	0.9	0.2-3.5

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